

The Apollonius Circles of rank k

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The purpose of this article is to introduce the notion of **Apollonius circle of rank k** and generalize some results on Apollonius circles.

Definition 1. It is called an **internal cevian of rank k** the line AA_k where $A_k \in (BC)$, such that $\frac{BA}{A_kC} = \left(\frac{AB}{AC}\right)^k$ ($k \in \mathbb{R}$).

If A'_k is the harmonic conjugate of the point A_k in relation to B and C , we call the line AA'_k an **outside cevian of rank k** .

Definition 2. We call **Apollonius circle of rank k** with respect to the side BC of ABC triangle the circle which has as diameter the segment line $A_kA'_k$.

Theorem 1. Apollonius circle of rank k is the locus of points M from ABC triangle's plan, satisfying the relation: $\frac{MB}{MC} = \left(\frac{AB}{AC}\right)^k$.

Proof. Let O_{A_k} the center of the Apollonius circle of rank k relative to the side BC of ABC triangle (see [Figure 1](#)) and U, V the points of intersection of this circle with the circle circumscribed to the triangle ABC . We denote by D the middle of arc BC , and we extend DA_k to intersect the circle circumscribed in U' . In $BU'C$ triangle, $U'D$ is bisector; it follows that $\frac{BA_k}{A_kC} = \frac{U'B}{U'C} = \left(\frac{AB}{AC}\right)^k$, so U' belongs to the locus. The perpendicular in U' on $U'A_k$ intersects BC on A''_k , which is the foot of the BUC triangle's outer bisector, so the harmonic conjugate

of A_k in relation to B and C , thus $A''_k = A'_k$. Therefore, U' is on the Apollonius circle of rank k relative to the side BC , hence $U' = U$.

Figure 1

Let M a point that satisfies the relation from the statement; thus $\frac{MB}{MC} = \frac{BA_k}{A_kC}$; it follows – by using the reciprocal of bisector's theorem – that MA_k is the internal bisector of angle BMC . Now let us proceed as before, taking the external bisector; it follows that M belongs to the Apollonius circle of center O_{A_k} . We consider now a point M on this circle, and we construct C' such that $\sphericalangle BNA_k \equiv \sphericalangle A_kNC'$ (thus NA_k is the internal bisector of the angle $\widehat{BNC'}$). Because $A'_kN \perp NA_k$, it follows that A_k and A'_k are harmonically conjugated with respect to B and C' . On the other hand, the same points are harmonically conjugated with respect to B and C ; from here, it follows that $C' = C$, and we have $\frac{NB}{NC} = \frac{BA_k}{A_kC} = \left(\frac{AB}{AC}\right)^k$.

Definition 3. It is called a **complete quadrilateral** the geometric figure obtained from a convex quadrilateral by extending the opposite sides until they intersect. A complete quadrilateral has 6 vertices, 4 sides and 3 diagonals.

Theorem 2. In a complete quadrilateral, the three diagonals' means are collinear (Gauss - 1810).

Proof. Let $ABCDEF$ a given complete quadrilateral (see [Figure 2](#)). We denote by H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4 respectively the orthocenters of ABF, ADE, CBE, CDF triangles, and let A_1, B_1, F_1 the feet of the heights of ABF triangle.

Figure 2

As previously shown, the following relations occur: $H_1A \cdot H_1A_1 - H_1B \cdot H_1B_1 = H_1F \cdot H_1F_1$; they express that the point H_1 has equal powers to the circles of diameters AC, BD, EF , because those circles contain respectively the points A_1, B_1, F_1 , and H_1 is an internal point. It is shown analogously that the points H_2, H_3, H_4 have equal powers to the same circles, so those points are situated on the radical axis (common to the circles), therefore the circles are part of a

fascicle, as such their centers – which are the means of the complete quadrilateral's diagonals – are collinear. The line formed by the means of a complete quadrilateral's diagonals is called **Gauss line** or **Gauss-Newton line**.

Theorem 3. The Apollonius circles of rank k of a triangle are part of a fascicle.

Proof. Let AA_k, BB_k, CC_k be concurrent cevians of rank k and AA'_k, BB'_k, CC'_k be the external cevians of rank k (see [Figure 3](#)). The figure $B'_kC_kB_kC'_kA_kA'_k$ is a complete quadrilateral and [Theorem 2](#) is applied.

Figure 3

Theorem 4. The Apollonius circles of rank k of a triangle are the orthogonals of the circle circumscribed to the triangle.

Proof. We unite O to D and U (see [Figure 1](#)), $OD \perp BC$ and $m(\widehat{A_kUA'_k}) = 90^\circ$, it follows that $\widehat{UA'_kA_k} = \widehat{ODA_k} = \widehat{OUA_k}$. The congruence $\widehat{UA'_kA_k} \equiv \widehat{OUA_k}$ shows that OU is tangent to the Apollonius circle of center O_{A_k} . Analogously, it can be demonstrated for the other Apollonius circles.

Remark 1. [The previous Theorem](#) indicates that the radical axis of Apollonius circles of rank k is the perpendicular taken from O to the line $O_{A_k}O_{B_k}$.

Theorem 5. The centers of Apollonius circles of rank k of a triangle are situated on the trilinear polar associated to the intersection point of the cevians of rank $2k$.

Proof. From [the previous Theorem](#), it results that $OU \perp UO_{A_k}$, so UO_{A_k} is an external cevian of rank 2 for BCU triangle, thus an external symmedian. Henceforth, $\frac{O_{A_k}B}{O_{A_k}C} = \left(\frac{BU}{CU}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{AB}{AC}\right)^{2k}$ (the last equality occurs because U belong to the Apollonius circle of rank k associated to the vertex A).

Theorem 6. The Apollonius circles of rank k of a triangle intersect the circle circumscribed to the triangle in two points that belong to the internal and external cevians of rank $k + 1$.

Proof. Let U and V points of intersection of the Apollonius circle of center O_{A_k} with the circle circumscribed to the ABC (see [Figure 1](#)). We take from U and V the perpendiculars UU_1, UU_2 and VV_1, VV_2 on AB and AC respectively. The quadrilaterals $ABVC, ABCU$ are inscribed, it follows the similarity of triangles BVV_1, CVV_2 and BUU_1, CUU_2 , from where we get the relations:

$$\frac{BV}{CV} = \frac{VV_1}{VV_2}, \quad \frac{UB}{UC} = \frac{UU_1}{UU_2}.$$

But $\frac{BV}{CV} = \left(\frac{AB}{AC}\right)^k, \frac{UB}{UC} = \left(\frac{AB}{AC}\right)^k, \frac{VV_1}{VV_2} = \left(\frac{AB}{AC}\right)^k$ and $\frac{UU_1}{UU_2} = \left(\frac{AB}{AC}\right)^k$, relations that show that V and U belong respectively to the internal cevian and the external cevian of rank $k + 1$.

Definition 4. If the Apollonius circles of rank k associated with a triangle have two common points, then we call these points isodynamic points of rank k (and we denote them W_k, W'_k).

Property 1. If W_k, W'_k are isodynamic centers of rank k , then:
 $W_k A \cdot BC^k = W_k B \cdot AC^k = W_k C \cdot AB^k$; $W'_k A \cdot BC^k = W'_k B \cdot AC^k = W'_k C \cdot AB^k$.

The proof of this property follows immediately from [Theorem 1](#).

Remark 2. The Apollonius circles of rank 1 are the investigated Apollonius circles (the bisectors are cevians of rank 1). If $k = 2$, the internal cevians of rank 2 are the symmedians, and the external cevians of rank 2 are the external symmedians, i.e. the tangents in triangle's vertices to the circumscribed circle. In this case, for the Apollonius circles of rank 2, [Theorem 3](#) becomes:

Theorem 7. The Apollonius circles of rank 2 intersect the circumscribed circle to the triangle in two points belonging respectively to the antibisector's isogonal and to the cevian outside of it.

The proof follows from [the Proof of Theorem 6](#). We mention that the antibisector is isotomic to the bisector, and a cevian of rank 3 is isogonic to the antibisector.

References.

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